

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Improving Dissolution of Artesunate from Immediate Release Tablet by Inclusion with Beta B-Cyclodextrin: In Vitro Characterization

Rajendra Surawase*¹, Kishor Kothawade², Avish Maru¹

¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Loknete Dr. J. D. Pawar College of Pharmacy, Manur, Kalwan, Nashik- 423 501

²Shree Gurudatta Shikshan Sanstha College of Pharmacy, Manur, Kalwan, Nashik- 423 501

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 28 Jun. 2025

Keywords:

Artesunate, Inclusion complexes, beta-cyclodextrin, Immediate release, Dissolution

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15762575

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to use an inclusion complex to increase the solubility of the medication artesunate. The kneading process prepared inclusion complexes of beta cyclodextrins and artesunate. In vitro dissolution tests and saturation solubility analysis were used to assess how the creation of inclusion complexes affected the drug solubility and dissolution. The infrared spectroscopy (IR) method was used to evaluate the complexes. The equimolar quantities of β -cyclodextrin and artesunate in the inclusion complex were then directly compressed into tablets and tested for several in-process quality control parameters. According to saturation solubility experiments, the drug solubility was enhanced by the beta cyclodextrin-PVP-K30 inclusion complex at a molar ratio of 1:2:1. FT-IR demonstrated that inclusion complexes were formed. In contrast to the pure medication, the produced inclusion complex tablets dissolved more quickly. To increase the solubility and dissolution of the poorly soluble medication, Artesunate can be complexed with β -cyclodextrin and PVP-K30.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important health issues the nation is dealing with is malaria. Multiple drug resistance is the primary drawback of conventional chemotherapy for malaria. Derivatives of artemisinin are among the few antimalarial medications that continue to work against strains

of Plasmodium falciparum malaria that are resistant to several medicines^{1,2}. To improve solubility and bioavailability, several liposomes and nanoparticles have been used. Nevertheless, there aren't many thorough investigations on cyclodextrin complexes available. Therefore, the current study focusses on the beta-cyclodextrin inclusion complex in order to enhance the

*Corresponding Author: Rajendra Surawase

Address: Department of Pharmaceutics, Loknete Dr. J. D. Pawar College of Pharmacy, Manur, Kalwan, Nashik- 423 501

Email ✉: rajendra.surawase@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

solubility and dissolution of immediate-release tablets.^{2,3}

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

The source of artesunate was Aquatic Remedies in Mumbai, India. High-purity analytical grades were used for all other compounds, and beta-cyclodextrin was acquired from Modern Industries in Nashik, Maharashtra, India.

METHODS

Spectrometric analysis

In accordance with IP, artesunate was recognized using formal identification tests, such as melting point, solubility, and description. Artesunate dissolved in methanol was examined in the UV spectrum between 200 and 400 nm to find high absorption bands that are indicative of the drug. 10 mg of the drug were precisely weighed and added to a 100 ml volumetric flask in order to reach a concentration of 100 µg/ml. Further diluting this resulted in a solution with a concentration of 5–30 µg/ml. Plotting the absorbance of these solutions versus concentration allowed for the creation of the standard calibration curve^{3,4}.

Phase solubility Studies

Using a gravimetric approach, the solubility of Artesunate in different solvents was assessed. A precisely weighed graded quantity of the drug was introduced to 10 millilitres of the various solvents in a stoppered glass container⁴. A shaker was used to shake the bottles following every addition. When no more drug entered the solution, the additional drug was stopped, and the bottles were shaken for a full day. To determine the solubility of a medication in a given solvent system, the weight of the drug up to the "saturation point," which is the point at which no more drug dissolves in the solvent, was taken into account^{5,6}.

Preparation of Inclusion complex

This was made using PVP K-30 (1:0.5,1:1,1:0.5) and artesunate and the β-cyclodextrin in different molar ratios (1:3, 1:2, and 1:1), as indicated in Table 1. Initially, β-cyclodextrin was combined with a small amount of 50% ethanol to make a paste, they were triturated in a glass mortar⁷. After adding the API kneaded for an hour. The result was then ground up, sieved through an 80 µm sieve, and kept in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride after being air dried for 24 hours at room temperature (28°C)^{7,8}.

Table 1: Formulation code for inclusion complexes

Formulation code	Composition	Ratio
IC1	Artesunate: Beta Cyclodextrin	1:1
IC2	Artesunate: Beta Cyclodextrin	1:2
IC3	Artesunate: Beta Cyclodextrin	1:3
IC4	Artesunate: Beta Cyclodextrin: PVP	1:1:0.5
IC5	Artesunate: Beta Cyclodextrin: PVP	1:2:1
IC6	Artesunate: Beta Cyclodextrin: PVP	1:3:1.5

Infrared spectroscopy

An IR spectrophotometer (Brooker) was used to perform Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

experiments on artesunate, β-cyclodextrin, and inclusion complex. Spectra were obtained using the KBr disc procedure. The spectra that were acquired were examined^{6,8}.

Characterization of inclusion complex

The flow characteristics of inclusion complexes for batches IC1 to IC6 were assessed. The tapped density device was used to determine bulk density and tapped densities three times. A precisely weighed 10-gramme powder of inclusion complex was added to a 100 ml graduated cylinder, and the cylinder was then left to tap after the initial volume was noted^{5,6,9}.

Percentage practical yield

The yield obtained from the process is what determines its efficiency. In order to determine the yield or efficiency, the percentage of practical yield was computed; this aids in the selection of the most suitable production process. To calculate the practical yield using the following equation, beta CD complexes were gathered and weighed^{6,7,8}.

$$\% \text{ Practical Yield} = \frac{\text{Practical mass inclusion complex}}{\text{theoretical Mass (Drug + Carrier)}} \times 100$$

In-Vitro release

Dissolution tests were conducted for all formulations (IC1 to IC6) at 50 rpm and 37 ± 0.5°C. The dissolution medium used was 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl. The samples were taken out at appropriate intervals of 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45, and 60 minutes, and their volume was replaced with an equivalent volume of the same medium. The samples underwent filtration and dilution. Using a UV-visible spectrophotometer, the absorbances of the resultant solutions were determined at 230 nm^{7,9,10}.

Saturation solubility tests were performed to assess the rise in artesunate solubility following complex formation with CDs: A known excess of CD compounds was added to 10 millilitres of distilled water. A rotary flask shaker was used to shake the samples for 24 hours at room temperature. After filtering and appropriately diluting the samples, they were spectrophotometrically examined at 230 nm. The pure drug's saturation solubility was also ascertained^{7,11,12}.

Drug content

In a 50 ml volumetric flask, 100 mg of precisely weighed compound was dissolved in 40 ml of methanol. Methanol was used to bring the solution up to volume. After that, the solution was appropriately diluted with 0.1 N HCl, and the drug concentration was measured at 230 nm using the UV spectrophotometric technique^{7,11}.

Formulation of Immediate release tablet

The artesunate: β-CD complex, which included 25 mg of artesunate, was compressed using the direct compression method to create tablets. After combining the complex, lactose, and maize starch were added and stirred for a further five minutes. After that, the mixture was compacted into tablet form. The tablets thickness, diameter, weight consistency, hardness, friability, dissolution time, and disintegration were all assessed^{12,13}.

Saturation solubility study

Table 2: Formulation code of Artesunate inclusion complex tablet

Ingredients	Formulations					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Inclusion complex of Artesunate equivalent to 25 mg	50	75	100	62.5	100	137.5
Starch	10	10	10	10	10	10
Talc	4	4	4	4	4	4
Magnesium stearate	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Lactose	134.5	109.5	84.5	122	84.5	47
Total weight	200	200	200	200	200	200

Evaluation of Immediate release tablet

To determine the tablet thickness, Vernier callipers were used. All the IPQC tests were carried out. A glass mortar and pestle were used to weigh five tablets and grind them into powder. In a 50 ml volumetric flask, 100 mg of precisely weighed powder was dissolved in methanol. Drug estimation was carried out using UV spectrophotometer at 230 nm^{14,15,16}.

In-vitro dissolution study

Dissolution equipment Type II was used to conduct the dissolution experiments of immediate-release tablets. 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl was used for the dissolution study. The temperature was kept at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ while the stirring speed was set at 50

rpm. At regular intervals, the samples were taken out and replaced with new dissolving media. UV spectrophotometer was used to filter, dilute, and analyze the materials at 230 nm^{16,17,18}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spectrometric analysis

The Artesunate solution's wavelength of maximum absorbance was determined to be 230 nm, which was consistent with the literature that was provided. As seen in Fig. 1, the absorbance versus concentration curve for artesunate was found to be linear across the 5–30 mg/ml range, demonstrating adherence to Beer and Lambert's laws³.

Figure 1: (a) Chemical structure of Artesunate (b) UV Spectrum of Artesunate (c) chemical structure of beta-cyclodextrin (d) calibration curve of Artesunate

Phase solubility Studies

A variety of solvents were used to test Artesunate solubility. According to the findings, the drug is sparingly soluble in 0.1 N HCl and acetic acid and

insoluble in water. Fig. 2 displays the solubility findings. Pure artesunate has a low aqueous solubility, as evidenced by its 1.32 mg/ml solubility in distilled water^{5,9,11}.

Figure 2: Solubility Study of Artesunate in Different Solvent

IR

Figure 3 shows the IR spectra of artesunate and its complexes over the 500–4500 cm⁻¹ frequency

range. The O-H stretching vibration caused the distinctive IR peaks of the artemether to appear at 3198.08 cm⁻¹. The FTIR spectrum of the inclusion complex corresponds to the beta-cyclodextrin,

with no major peaks corresponding to Artesunate^{6,7,18}.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3: IR Spectrum of (a) Artesunate (b) beta-cyclodextrin (c) mixture of artesunate and beta-cyclodextrin

Solubility Study

Solubility study findings demonstrated that β -CD was a useful carrier for improving the solubility of medications that were not very soluble.

Figure 4: Saturation solubility study of ART-BCD inclusion complex in water

Characterization of inclusion complex

The percentage yield and drug content of each batch of drug inclusion complexes were assessed.

Table 3% yield from 94.60 to 98.89, while the percentage drug content ranged from 96.56 to 99.36.

Table 3: Characterization of Inclusion complexes

Formulation	Percentage Yield	Percentage Drug Content
IC1	94.60	96.56
IC2	95.32	97.36
IC3	97.85	98.52
IC4	96.56	97.24
IC5	98.89	99.36
IC6	97.63	98.41

Figure 5: Percentage of drug content of BCD inclusion complexes

All of the formulation's angles of repose were observed to range between 21.56 and 30.54°. These have adequate flow characteristics because they are all less than 40°. Tapped density ranged from 0.63 to 0.66 g/cm³, whereas bulk density was

determined to be between 0.51 and 0.58 g/cm³. In all of the formulations, Carr's index values are less than 20 %. As a result, the formulations have suitable flow characteristics^{10,11,19}.

Table 4: Micrometric properties of inclusion complexes

Batch Code	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Tapped density (g/cm ³)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner ratio	Angle of repose (θ)
IC1	0.52	0.63	17.46	1.21	29.87
IC2	0.56	0.66	15.15	1.17	28.56
IC3	0.53	0.64	17.18	1.20	27.45
IC4	0.51	0.63	19.04	1.23	30.54
IC5	0.57	0.64	10.76	1.12	21.56
IC6	0.58	0.65	10.76	1.12	22.36

Table 5: Percent Cumulative dissolution of Inclusion Complexes

Time (Min)	Percent Cumulative Release of Complexes					
	IC1	IC2	IC3	IC4	IC5	IC6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	30.31	33.45	37.48	42.47	58.57	52.63
10	35.38	38.48	42.51	47.48	65.59	57.68
15	40.51	43.53	47.48	52.58	70.79	62.61
30	47.58	50.59	55.18	60.63	79.85	69.68
45	57.18	60.19	65.29	70.71	89.23	79.28
60	75.80	82.69	85.77	87.88	97.98	92.98

Figure 6: In vitro release study of BCD complexes**Evaluation of Immediate release tablet**

All of the formula tablets dissolve rapidly. The manufactured immediate-release tablet has a

disintegration duration of 18 to 30 seconds. Within 18 seconds, the formulation containing the Artesunate- β -CD (1:2:1) – PVP K-30 inclusion complex completely disintegrated.

Table 6: Physicochemical Properties of Artesunate BCD inclusion tablet

Tablet Property	Formulations					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Thickness (mm)	4.3±0.18	4.4±0.17	4.5±0.12	4.3±0.12	4.5±0.15	4.4±0.19
Uniformity of weight (mg)	201±0.12	202±0.13	199±0.13	198±0.18	201±0.14	202±0.14
Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	4.5±0.11	5.0±0.12	5.2±0.13	4.8±0.16	4.6±0.14	5.3±0.17
Drug content (%)	97.23	98.25	97.88	98.45	99.45	98.45
Disintegration time (Sec)	30	27	30	19	18	21
Friability (%)	0.875	0.785	0.925	0.845	0.825	0.926

In vitro release study

Drug release from formulations including BCD complexes ranged from 73.79 to 96.76%,

according to *in vitro* release tests. Compared to other formulations, Formulation F5 demonstrated a quicker rate of drug release^{11,12,13,20}.

Table 7: Percent Cumulative Drug Release of BCD Inclusion Immediate Release Tablet

Time (Min)	Percent Cumulative Drug Release of Immediate Release Tablet					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	28.32	31.31	34.38	40.49	56.59	50.61
10	33.32	36.41	40.59	44.49	63.32	55.61
15	38.21	41.51	45.38	50.51	68.71	60.69
30	45.51	48.52	53.19	58.61	77.82	67.61
45	55.18	58.11	63.28	68.69	86.34	75.23
60	73.79	80.63	83.68	85.81	96.76	90.31

Figure 7: In vitro release study of BCD complex immediate-release tablet

The solubility of artesunate with BCD increased. The BCD systems' effectiveness of β -CD complexation and solubilization have been improved by including a small quantity of the hydrophilic polymer PVP K-30. Artesunate CD complex with β -CD (1:2) and PVP (1%) had the maximum solubility. As seen in Figure 4, the formation of a stable inclusion complex between Artesunate and BCD is mostly responsible for the complex increased solubility^{8,9}. All of the formulations had acceptable flow properties, with the Hausner ratio values falling below 1.5 and

falling between 1.12-1.23 as seen in Table 4, at one hour, the percentage release of inclusion complexes ranged from 75.80% to 97.98%. The dissolving rate of all inclusion complex tablets was higher than that of tablets made with the drug alone. When compared to tablets made with β -CD inclusion complexes, those made with β -CD and PVP K30 inclusion complexes had greater dissolving values. Solubility have been significantly improved by the addition of PVP^{12,13,21}.

CONCLUSION

The Artesunate and β -CD and Artesunate- β -CD PVP K30 ternary solid inclusion complexes were prepared in this study using the kneading method. According to saturation solubility studies, the drug's solubility was improved. They dissolve faster than tablets with a 1:2 M ratio of the artesunate- β -CD complex than tablets containing pure medicines. More research on the novel artesunate- β -CD complex might lead to artesunate-combination treatment with better bioavailability, which would help cure malaria more successfully.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am grateful for the laboratory facilities provided by Loknete Dr. J. D. Pawar College of Pharmacy at Kalwan, Nashik. The research was not funded by any agency, and the authors alone is responsible for all costs.

REFERENCES

1. Bashir A, Abdel-Hamid S, Badawi A, Geneidi AS. Enhancing dissolution of artesunate from immediate release tablets using a green granulation technique. *Arch Pharm Sci ASU*. (2019);3(1): 55-77. DOI:10.21608/aps.2019.20230.
2. Chaudhary VB, Patel JK. Cyclodextrin inclusion complex to enhance solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. (2013);4(1):68. [http://dx.doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.4\(1\).68-76](http://dx.doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.4(1).68-76)
3. Jain PS, Chaudhari AJ, Patel SA, Patel ZN, Patel DT. Development and validation of the UV-spectrophotometric method for determination of terbinafine hydrochloride in bulk and in formulation. *Pharm Methods*. (2011);2(3):198-202. DOI: 10.4103/2229-4708.90364.
4. Badawi A, Geneidi AS. Enhancing dissolution of artesunate from immediate-release tablets using a green granulation technique. *Archives of Pharmaceutical Sciences Ain Shams University*. (2019);3(1):55-77. DOI:10.21608/aps.2019.20230
5. Mandadapu, G., Kolli, P., & Kurra, V. G. Formulation & evaluation of cyclodextrin complexed tablets by enhancing the dissolution rate. *Journal of Innovations in Applied Pharmaceutical Science*. (2022);7(3):123-132. <https://doi.org/10.37022/jiaps.v7i3.375>
6. Yahaya ZS, Ofokansi KC, Allagh ST, Bhatia PG. Preparation and characterization of artemether inclusion complexes with hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. (2017);16(10):2359-64. DOI:10.4314/tjpr.v16i10.7
7. De Miranda JC, Martins TE, Veiga F, Ferraz HG. Cyclodextrins and ternary complexes: Technology to improve solubility of poorly soluble drugs. *Braz J Pharm Sci* (2011); 47:666-78. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1984-82502011000400003>
8. Challa R, Ahuja A, Ali J, Khar RK. Cyclodextrins in drug delivery: An updated review. *AAPS Pharm SciTech*. (2005);6(2): E329-57. DOI: 10.1208/pt060243
9. Durk MR, Jones NS, Liu J, Nagapudi K, Mao C, Plise EG, Wong S, Chen JZ, Chen Y, Chinn LW, Chiang PC. Understanding the Effect of Hydroxypropyl- β -Cyclodextrin on Fenebrutinib Absorption in an Itraconazole-Fenebrutinib Drug-Drug Interaction Study. *Clin Pharmacol Ther*. (2020);108(6):1224-1232. DOI: 10.1002/cpt.1943
10. Renuka Sagane, Kiran B. Erande, Solubility Enhancement, Formulation and Evaluation of

- Dolutegravir, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, (2024);2(1): 206-213. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443939>
11. Joshi M, Pathak S, Sharma S, Patravale V. Solid microemulsion preconcentrate (NanOsorb) of artemether for effective treatment of malaria. *Int J Pharm.* (2008);362(1-2):172-8. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2008.06.012
 12. Deshmukh AS, Tiwari KJ, Mahajan VR. Solubility Enhancement Techniques for Poorly Water-Soluble Drugs. (2017);10(3):3701-8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37285/ijpsn.2017.10.3.1>
 13. Xiuling Li, Shunung Liang, Chee Hwee Tan, et al. Nanocarriers in the Enhancement of Therapeutic Efficacy of Natural Drugs. *BIOI.* (2021);2(2):40-49. DOI: 10.15212/bioi-2020-0040.
 14. Zwanden Sule Yahaya, Kenneth C Ofokansi, Suzane T Allagh and Pat G Bhatia, Preparation and characterization of artemether inclusion complexes with hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.* (2017); 16 (10): 2359-2364. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v16i10.7>.
 15. Kasama Pongsamart, Waree Limwikanr, Uracha Rungsardthong Ruktanonchai, Nattawut Charoenthai, Satit Puttipipatkachorn, Preparation, characterization and antimalarial activity of dihydroartemisinin / β -cyclodextrin spray-dried powder, *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology.* (2022); 73: 103434, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2022.103434>
 16. García A, Leonardi D, Salazar MO, Lamas MC. Modified β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex to improve the physicochemical properties of albendazole. complete in vitro evaluation and characterization. (2014);9(2): e88234. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0088234
 17. Hao Y, Chen S, Tian L, et al. Inclusion complex of Artemether with 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin for the treatment of malaria: preparation, characterization and evaluation. *MOJ Bioequiv Availab.* (2017);3(6):145-151. DOI: 10.15406/mojbb.2017.03.00052
 18. Carneiro SB, Costa Duarte FÍ, Heimfarth L, Siqueira Quintans JdS, Quintans-Júnior LJ, Veiga Júnior VFd, Neves de Lima ÁA. Cyclodextrin–Drug Inclusion Complexes: In Vivo and In Vitro Approaches. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences.* (2019); 20(3):642. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20030642>
 19. Sârcea L, Tănase I-M, Ledeti A, Cîrcioban D, Vlase G, Barvinschi P, Miclău M, Văruț R-M, Trandafirescu C, Ledeti I. Encapsulation of Risperidone by Methylated β -Cyclodextrins: Physicochemical and Molecular Modeling Studies. *Molecules.* (2020); 25(23):5694. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25235694>
 20. Adebayo, J.O., Tijjani, H., Adegunloye, A.P. et al. Enhancing the antimalarial activity of artesunate. *Parasitol Res.* (2020);119: 2749–2764 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-020-06786-1>
 21. Shende, P., Desai, P., Gaud, R. S., & Dhumatkar, R. Engineering of microcomplex of artemether and lumefantrine for effective drug treatment in malaria. *Artificial Cells, Nanomedicine, and Biotechnology.* (2016);45(8): 1597–1604. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21691401.2016.1267012>

HOW TO CITE: Rajendra Surawase*, Kishor Kothawade, Avish Maru, Improving Dissolution of Artesunate from Immediate Release Tablet by Inclusion with Beta B-Cyclodextrin: In Vitro Characterization, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 5492-5503. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15762575>

